

ОПЫТ ДИСТАНЦИОННОГО ОБУЧЕНИЯ

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DISTANCE TEACHING EXPERIENCE

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Определение термина «дистанционное» не может быть ограничено только удаленностью от учебной среды, такой как школа, поскольку большинство учащихся дистанционного обучения находятся недалеко от своих школ и могут получить доступ к учебным материалам через электронные средства массовой информации. Вот почему «расстояние» в физическом смысле не является существенным фактором с точки зрения образования. Рассмотрена эффективность дистанционного обучения. Более того, экспериментальная часть описана в данной статье.

Abstract

The definition of the term “distance” cannot be limited only by being far away from the teaching environment like school since the majority of pupils in distance education are close to their schools and can access teaching materials through electronic media. That’s why “distance” in physical sense is not an essential factor in the perspective of education. The effectiveness of distance learning is considered. Moreover, the experimental part is described in the given article.

Ключевые слова: дистанционное обучение, экспериментальная часть, задания.

Keywords: distance learning, experimental part, tasks.

Introduction. The definition of the term “distance” cannot be limited only by being far away from the teaching environment like school since the majority of pupils in distance education are close to their schools and can access teaching materials through electronic media. That’s why “distance” in physical sense is not an essential factor in the perspective of education [1].

Kaya regarded distance education as a discipline which provides lifelong education for anyone who wants to solve the inequality of opportunity, as well as contributing to the realization of a number of individual and social goals of education and based on self-learning [2].

Uşun defined distance education as a planned and systematic educational technology application [3]. Moore and Kearsley used the term “distance education” instead of “distance learning and teaching” because education was more comprehensive term that including both learning and teaching in accordance to just learning or teaching and according to Moore and Kearsley, distance education was both teaching and learning process that take places in the separation in space and time; requires elements of interaction via use of technologies [4]. Distance education can also be defined as the transmission of information electronically to a remote place via satellite, video, sound, computer, multimedia technology and similar tools, or as an education system where the teacher and the student are located in different places [5]. Given all the definitions above, it is seen that the concept of distance education emerges as learning and teaching model in independent of time and space and provides educational opportunities through technologies [6].

Discussion. During the first two weeks of our active internship, the theme of the lesson was “Plans and dreams”. They learned and practised grammar structure

“be going to” to talk about plans and intentions, and new words concerning airports. They also developed their listening, reading and writing skills.

The experimental group pupils were invited to the class using a link and invitations to their email addresses. In their online class, the experimental group first participated in a discussion. As a warming-up, they were asked to answer the questions: When were you at an airport? Where did you go? Why? Warm-up tasks should not be difficult and long to complete, both in online and traditional training. We chose this way of working so that pupils began to get used to communicating in the blog. The Blog option in Google classroom can serve to develop pupils' writing and communication skills.

Then, the student was given an assignment in a Google form in order to learn new words. The advantage of Google Forms is that it can be used not only to assess the knowledge of pupils, but also to teach some elements of grammar or vocabulary. Pupils could see the correct answers immediately after completing the assignment. Thus, they learn new words inductively. This assignment was also a pre-listening task. For while-listening, pupils were asked to listen to the audio and answer short questions. Google Classroom has a function of attaching documents to tasks. Pupils can edit their copy and send it to the teacher for review. The next task was to listen to the text and fill in the table according to the information in the audio and send it to the teacher for verification. The teacher can leave notes for the student and send him the grade.

The next task was to listen to the audio again and fill in the main character's plans table. The final step was filling out a reflective form, where pupils had to describe three things they learned after the lesson, two things that are still interesting to them, and one thing

that they still have questions about. Basically, the pupils answered that they learned more than three new words. About what was interesting for them, some pupils noted that using online platforms when learning English was interesting for them. The pupils still had questions about how the “going to” construct that they encountered in the audio assignment is used.

The first stage of the second lesson in Google Classroom pupils watched a video regarding to the airport. While watching the video they were supposed to complete the dialogue with ‘be going to’ + one of the verbs. Then we asked them to listen to it again to check their answers.

After watching the video, the pupils completed the sentences with “going to” and the correct verbs in an assignment that was created in Google Forms. After completing the assignments, you can connect the function of showing answers immediately after completing the assignments, so that pupils can see their mistakes and work on not repeating them in the future.

Then, the pupils in pairs were supposed to have a conversation about their travel plans using the given information. For this, the pupils were sent an assignment on Google Docs. Google Docs is essentially Microsoft Word, Excel, and PowerPoint, but available online for free. Documents can be shared with others and are available anytime for anyone who has permission to co-edit or view.

By providing a shared work and personal learning environment, Google Docs effectively integrates opposing learning approaches. This is especially useful for teachers interested in differentiating their assignments. For example, thanks to the dualism offered by Google Docs, pupils focused on excellence in group work can get what they want by sharing their workspace. Moreover, the flexibility that Google Docs offers to pupils makes it a good tool for personal study space or e-portfolio. Similar to a wiki, pupils can use Google Docs to record and share what they learn. However, on Google Docs, this can be done in real time. Thus, pupils have the opportunity to transcend time and space. Cloud technologies can reach local or global audiences from anywhere in the world. After drawing up the dialogues for the road play, the course teacher has the opportunity to look at the document, see what kind of flattered the information, and then correct the mistakes and return their work to the pupils.

The final task for the second week was a quiz, which included grammar tasks accompanied by video and pictures. First, the pupils needed to watch the video “Grammar show” which we took from the BBC Learning English website. Pupils were supposed to revise the grammar structure and answer the questions. Then they were asked questions about the content of the video. The next assignment was to use the words in parentheses, complete the text with the appropriate tenses. Then, the pupils made up sentences with the help of the pictures offered to them.

When filling out the reflective form, pupils gave different answers. For example, the answer of one of the pupils was: “I learned about using “Be going to”. I found out that the structure is used for scheduling. Also, I learned about sentence structure in positive, negative

and question forms: I am going to learn English. I am not going to learn English. Am I going to learn English?”. “The video assignment was interesting for me,” replied another student. “I have a question about when the question word “when” is used,” another student replied to the third question.

At the same time, it is important to teach the student to understand which types of educational activities are easy for him, and which ones need to be worked on. The ability to assess the results of educational activities and determine how much they depend on its content allows them to teach the student to plan their future activities, build a self-development program and becomes the key to the success of learning English at the subsequent stages of education.

Self-esteem is a person's assessment of himself, his capabilities, qualities and place among other people. It is the level of self-esteem that largely determines the criticality, exactingness to oneself, attitude to success and failure, relationships with other people. That is why in the classroom, great attention should be paid to the organization of reflective activity, using the method of self-determination of pupils. Modern technologies suggest that the student must not only understand the content of the material, but also comprehend the ways and techniques of his work, be able to choose the most rational ones.

“What I've done?”, “For what purpose?”, “Why am I doing it like this?”, “What result did I get?”, “Which option is better?” are the questions that are asked by pupils who possess reflection to be able to be aware of their activities. Each student formulates the results of the lesson using a diagram where he connects and summarizes his impressions, knowledge, skills.

Our Google class was called “Pre-Intermediate”, there were collected 5 online lessons for the development of independent learning and self-control among pupils of the specialty “Publishing”. Our task was to cover the following material see Table 1. We also add columns for TSIW and SIW. In Column TSIW we added materials which were used during the experiment. Moreover, we suggest SIW materials in order to develop pupils' independent work. The SIW materials which we have created are described in the last chapter of the practical part as recommended ones. Each lesson had the elements to develop pupils' ability to self-control and analyze the material they have learned.

During an active internship, we prepared online lessons and an online course for them to develop self-study and self-control. A variety of materials were presented in our training, namely:

presentations on the topics of the course; additional materials (articles, guidelines, links to documents, etc.) for self-study by pupils; practical assignments on certain methodological topics for independent implementation; control tasks (tests) and training tests, with the ability to see your result upon completion, get an assessment and comment; video lessons for independent viewing and analysis with methodological developments; tasks for self-control in the form of reflective tasks.

We distinguish the following types of assignments used to master the main material of the course on Google classroom:

1. tasks for choosing the correct answer, including the choice of one or more of the many and the choice of a word from the text;
2. formation of the construction of an answer based on the choice of the correct answers and the corresponding options, the choice of the correct answers and their arrangement in a certain sequence and the formulation of the answer from individual elements;
3. entering the correct answer, which involves writing a single word or phrase;
4. complex tasks that integrate skills of different levels, for example, grammatical skills and speaking skills.

Tasks for choosing the correct answer are aimed at controlling the level of formation of grammatical and lexical skills and, as a rule, are associated with the development of formal features of linguistic material.

Tasks of the type of formation of the answer and entering the correct answer are characterized by the absence of ready-made answer options, pupils formulate them and enter them using the keyboard. These tasks are associated with the integration of different skills (lexical, grammatical, spelling, etc.) and, when constructing an answer at the phrase level, they allow one to present the speech level of the formation of a foreign language communicative competence.

Conclusion. With all the positive feedback from pupils and their interest in such a form of foreign language teaching as a distance course, it should be pointed out that at the stage of developing assignments and uploading materials to Google classroom, teachers need to make a lot of efforts. Depending on the goals of the course, the teacher must think over the content and expediency of tasks (taking into account various types of speech activity), their number, mode of execution (educational or test), number of attempts, deadlines, etc. Particular attention should be paid to tasks with an

open answer, for example, writing essays, drafting dialogues. Such tasks are necessary for the formation of foreign language competence in productive types of speech activity, but, unlike closed ones (multiple choice, finding matches, etc.), Google classroom cannot automatically check them, but only fixes the time and date of completion. The teacher needs to decide whether he himself checks such works, when, how he evaluates, or, for example, using the possibilities of Google classroom, organizes a mutual examination by pupils. These difficulties arise only at the initial stage of work in the Google classroom virtual learning environment. Further in the process of work, especially in a friendly atmosphere of cooperation, the teachers themselves are involved with interest in this creative activity, anticipating an effective learning outcome and pupils' gratitude. Thus, the use of the developed electronic course to accompany practical classes primarily helps to optimize the organization of pupils' independent work, while developing their skills in autonomous educational activities.

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